

Recent advances in the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of nitrones

Avijit Banerji* and Debasish Bandyopadhyay

Centre of Advanced Studies on Natural Products, Department of Chemistry, Calcutta University, 92, A. P. C. Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : ablabcu@yahoo.co.uk Fax : 91-33-23519755

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This review outlines some recent developments in 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions of nitrones. An attempt has been made to focus on aspects which were comparatively less revealed earlier. Special emphasis has been given on reactions and their explanation on mechanistic and theoretical grounds, rather than on applications.

Introduction

Cycloaddition reactions are the most important category of pericyclic reactions¹⁻⁵ if synthetic utility is taken as the criterion. 1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions to multiple bonds constitute one of the most powerful synthetic methodologies for the construction of five-membered heterocycles. These are basically $[\pi^4s + \pi^2s]$ processes, the thermal (ground state) reaction being an 'allowed' reaction. These reactions often proceed with high regio- and stereoselectivity. Several reviews have appeared in earlier years on 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions⁶⁻¹⁰.

Nitronium is an important example of an 1,3-dipolar species; [(1) \leftrightarrow (2)]. The synthetic potential of nitroniums is based primarily on two factors. The first one is their high reactivity towards a wide range of dipolarophiles: electron-deficient, electron-rich or non-activated species, to afford five-membered heterocyclic systems. The second feature is that the resulting heterocycles, i.e. isoxazolines or isoxazolidines, have various synthetic useful functionalities masked in the rings, which can be released through ring cleavage giving easy access to a variety of differently functionalized open chain derivatives. Some of these can be transformed to other heterocyclic systems¹⁻⁵.

The $[\pi^4s + \pi^2s]$ cycloaddition of nitroniums has been analyzed by the Frontier Molecular Orbital (FMO) approach⁵⁻¹². The FMO interactions of the nitronium cycloaddition to an unsymmetrically substituted ethylenic double bond is shown in Fig. 1. The relative size of the lobes in the

Fig. 1

diagram reflect the relative magnitudes of the coefficients in the dipole HOMO and LUMO. The analysis shows that the *suprafacial-suprafacial* thermal cycloaddition would be an allowed process.

1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions are susceptible to electronic and steric influences which affect the nature of the transition state. Simple acyclic nitroniums are generally less reactive than aliphatic cyclic analogues. Sustmann¹³ classified 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions into three types depending on whether the dominant interaction is:

- between the dipole-HOMO and the dipolarophile-LUMO;
- between the dipole-LUMO and the dipolarophile-HOMO; or
- both the interactions are of similar significance.

Electron-donating (including alkyl) and conjugating substituents increase the energies of both HOMO and LUMO, whereas electron-withdrawing and conjugating substituents decrease the energies of both HOMO and LUMO^{14,15}. The Frontier Molecular Orbital (FMO) interactions also account for the regioselectivity of cycloaddition¹⁶. Steric factors and secondary orbital interactions usually dictate the stereochemical outcome of the cycloaddi-

tion^{10,13-15,17,18}. 1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions of nitrones are reversible and therefore theoretically subject to both thermodynamic and kinetic control. However, the cycloreversion reaction usually faces a large activation barrier, as a result of which it is the relative rates of the different possibilities for the forward reaction which determines the overall regio- and stereochemical courses. Thus the 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions are subject essentially to kinetic control in most cases.

1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions of nitrones with unsaturated systems are the best chemical processes for the construction of reduced isoxazole ring systems in high yields⁶⁻¹⁰. Torsell has reviewed the work done till the late 1980s in an excellent monograph¹⁰. Since then, a shorter and less comprehensive review has appeared in the series "Comprehensive Organic Synthesis" edited by Trost and Fleming⁹. After the publication of these reviews, a large number of interesting papers have appeared on nitrono cycloadditions. The present review therefore deals with the publications on nitrono cycloadditions which have appeared in the last few years, with special emphasis on the intermolecular 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of cyclic nitrones. In this brief review an attempt has been made to enlighten those aspects which were comparatively less revealed earlier. Special emphasis has been given to theoretical approaches, several papers on which have appeared recently.

Recent examples of work done

A fair amount of work has been done with various cyclic nitrones. Worthy of note among these nitrones are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2

de March *et al.*¹⁹⁻²¹ have contributed significantly in recent years to the study of 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions. 1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions of 3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-*N*-oxide (4) to achiral and chiral *p*-benzoquinone monoketals, showed poor chemo- and stereoselectivity. Hence, a highly efficient strategy was set up by de March on the basis of the temporary conjugate addition of thiophenol to the dipolarophile^{19a,b}. The phenylthio derivative available in both enantiopure forms, were demonstrated to be effective as masked chiral synthetic equivalents of *p*-benzoquinone in the model reaction.

All the α,β -hexenolides and α,β -unsaturated esters demonstrated high stereoselectivity in their 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions to cyclic nitrones (3) and (4). For the *cis* dipolarophiles, it was reported that the *exo* transition state predominates over the *endo*, while for the *trans* dipolarophiles the opposite preference was observed²⁰.

With 1,2-disubstituted olefins, in which one of the substituents is an electron-withdrawing group, a high degree of regiocontrol is usually observed leading to isoxazolidine adducts with the electron-withdrawing substituent in the 4-position¹⁰. This is in agreement with FMO theory. Less predictable is the stereoselectivity of the process, since it depends on both electronic and steric factors. Only careful and detailed consideration of the competitive *endo*- and *exo*-transition states for each particular reaction may allow an explanation of the experimental results.

Reaction between nitrono 3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-*N*-oxide (4) and phenylthiolactone afforded the *exo-anti* cycloadduct as the major product (72%), with a minor percentage of the *exo-syn* isomer. The cycloaddition of nitrono (4) to crude lactone allowed the isolation of the *exo-anti* adduct as the only product, although in low yield (12% for the two consecutive steps).

Banerji *et al.*²¹ have been investigated the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of cyclic nitrono (3) with the piperidides of cinnamic acid and substituted cinnamic acids (7-9) in refluxing toluene solution. Two regioisomeric cycloadducts based on 2-aryl-3-piperidinyl-oxo-2,3,3a,4,5,6-hexahydropyrrolo-[1,2-*b*]isoxazole (10) and 3-aryl-2-piperidinyl-oxo-2,3,3a,4,5,6-hexahydropyrrolo-[1,2-*b*]isoxazole (11) (Scheme 1) were obtained. The structures and relative configurations (3,3a-*cis*) of the product were established on the basis of spectroscopic data and X-ray crystallographic analysis. Both regioisomeric products were obtained by the *endo* approach of the nitrono.

Scheme 1

Allylic bromo dipolarophiles (Fig. 3) shown as in the sequel below proved viable partners for cycloaddition to nitrones²², with the exception of the labile γ -bromobutenolide. The reactions of cyclic nitrones to these esters and lactones showed high diastereoselectivity; a preference

for the *endo* or *exo* transition state depended on the *E* or *Z* configuration of the dipolarophile.

Fig. 3

Brandi and coworkers²³ have reported 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions of nitrones 3,4-dihydroisoquinoline-*N*-oxide (5) and *C*-phenyl-*N*-methylnitron (12) to the functionally substituted methylenecyclopropane derivatives (13) and (14) (Fig. 4). The chlorine atom in the dipolarophiles plays a key role and by its nature of being a good leaving group,

Fig. 4

confers to the isoxazolidine adducts the possibility to undergo unprecedented types of ring reorganization which are made selective by the presence of an α -spiroannulated cyclopropane ring. The constitution of the nitron also plays an important role, as it determines the tendency of the cycloadduct to undergo cycloreversion reactions, known to be higher for cycloadducts of nitron (12); this in turn determines the outcome of the rearrangement process. Finally, the solvent polarity can be decisive, as more polar solvents in connection with the presence of the chloride leaving group can stabilize polar intermediates. This was observed here for the first time in the chemistry of 5-*spiro*-cyclopropane isoxazolidines. Such polar intermediates can lead to completely new processes with the selective and very efficient formation of new tetrahydro-1*H*-indolizin-5-ones. This study has also allowed the isolation and characterization of novel tricyclic and bicyclic cyclobutane-annulated isoxazolidines bearing a chlorine substituent on a bridge-head carbon atom α to an oxygen.

Ali and coworkers²⁴ first described a third generation nitron to provide an efficient and stereoselective entry into more complicated molecules. Interest in alkaloids having *cis*-2,5-disubstituted pyrrolidine moiety led them to explore the possibility of converting the *trans* cycloadducts to *cis*-2,5-disubstituted pyrrolidines. In an effort to prepare either the aldonitron or the ketonitron in a regioselective man-

ner, a series of nitron cycloaddition products was treated with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (*m*-CPBA) in different solvents. All of the 2-mono- and 2,2-disubstituted adducts were reported to undergo ring opening reaction in dichloromethane resulting in the exclusive formation of the less substituted nitron. However, there is a dramatic change in the product ratio as the solvent was switched from aprotic to protic. The authors have explained the results in the following way: for the carbocyclic counterpart of the five/five fused isoxazolidines the free energy difference of approximately 25 kJ mol⁻¹ favors the *cis* over the *trans* isomer. Although the presence of two hetero atoms in the five/five fused isoxazolidines somewhat decreases this energy difference, geometric constraints do not permit nitrogen inversion and lock it to remain *cis*-fused. The proposed mechanistic pathway envisages the intermediacy of the amine oxide intermediate, followed by nitroxonium salt, in which the secondary or tertiary alkoxide ion finds proton in its immediate vicinity for fast kinetic deprotonation to result in the exclusive formation of the less substituted nitron. Electrostatic attraction presumably holds the ion-pair close to each other and restricts rotation long enough to allow the selective deprotonation to occur. In protic solvent hydrogen bonding or fast proton capture by the species leads to the interception of the protonated intermediate which tautomerizes under thermodynamically controlled acid-catalyzed process resulting in the formation of the more substituted nitron as the sole or the predominant products^{24a,b}.

The stereochemistry and reactivity of the cycloaddition reactions of eight-membered cyclic nitron with several alkenes have also been studied by Ali *et al.*²⁵. The concentration of the nitron and alkene was kept low and high, respectively, in order to minimize polymerization of the nitron. The additions of styrene, methyl methacrylate and ethyl vinyl ether were found to be regioselective with oxygen of nitron functionality attaching itself to the more substituted end of the alkenes. They also determined the ratio of the nitron and alkene from time to time and the second order rate constants were obtained by linear regression analysis. The 8-membered nitron was found to be less reactive than its seven-membered counterpart. For medium sized rings larger than six membered, angle strain plays a minor part but eclipsing strain is introduced by the change of hybridization from *sp*² to *sp*³ of the atoms in the imine part of the nitron functionality. Cyclooctane is known to have greater eclipsing strain than cycloheptane and as such non-bonded repulsions are expected to be unfavorable in the transition state leading to the eight/five ring system. This could account for the slower rate of cycloaddition of the cyclic nitron.

Ali's nitronone-based approach thus provides an excellent entry to the *trans*- as well as the *cis*-2,5-dialkyl pyrrolidines. The scope and convenience of this sequence may very well be extended to construct piperidine derivatives, an important system in great many alkaloids. Results of the oxidation of hydroxylamines, peracid induced ring opening of several cycloadducts, and subsequent entry to *cis*- and *trans*-2,5-disubstituted pyrrolidines would indeed be helpful for the proper utilization of these high yielding reactions in incorporating and elaborating pyrrolidine rings^{24a,b}.

Banerji *et al.*¹⁶ have studied the cycloadditions of the four *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl nitrones to the acyclic dipolarophiles cinnamic acid piperidides as well as cyclic dipolarophiles, i.e. conjugated lactone butenolide, by refluxing the reactants in toluene under nitrogen atmosphere. In the later reaction series, two series of cycloadducts, viz. the 3,4-*trans*-4,5-*trans*-5-aryl-4-piperidinyloxisoxazolidines as major products and the diastereoisomeric 3,4-*cis*-4,5-*trans*-5-aryl-4-piperidinyloxisoxazolidines could be isolated as the minor one from all the reactions.

de March *et al.*²⁷ carried out a similar sequence of reactions starting with the five-membered nitronone (3) and butenolide. On oxidation with *m*-CPBA in CDCl₃, the cycloadduct gave only one 2-substituted nitronone. In an effort to introduce two lactone residues as substituents of the pyrrolidine ring, they performed the reaction between the nitronone with 2(*5H*)-furanone at 110°C. The newly formed cycloadduct on *m*-CPBA oxidation, followed by treatment with dimethylacetylenedicarboxylate (DMAD) gives one crystalline product in 34% yield. The cycloaddition leading to the formation of the final product should proceed through an *anti* approach and consequently the lactones should be in *cis* disposition.

Optically pure (*5R*)- [and (*5S*)]-5,6-dihydro-5-phenyl-2*H*-1,4-oxazin-2-one *N*-oxides [(*5R*)- and (*5S*)-16] were designed¹⁷ as chiral (*E*)-geometry-fixed α -alkoxycarbonyl nitrones (15). The nitrones (*5R*)- and (*5S*)-16 were synthesized by three-step oxidation of (*R*)- and (*S*)-2-hydroxylamino-2-phenylethanols [(*R*)- and (*S*)-17]. Condensation of the resulting (*R*)- and (*S*)-2-hydroxylamino-2-phenyl-ethanols [(*R*)- and (*S*)-19] with glyoxylic acid and cyclization gave the intermediary nitrones [(*R*)- and (*S*)-20b]. The nitronone (*5R*)-16 reacted with olefins under mild conditions to afford the corresponding cycloadducts as the main products which were formed via the least sterically demanding *exo* modes (Scheme 2).

Reagents : (i) *p*-Methoxybenzaldehyde, toluene, reflux; (ii) *m*-CPBA, CH₂Cl₂; (iii) NH₂OH.HCl, MeOH; (iv) OHC-CO₂R (R = H, Me).

Scheme 2

Cycloaddition of cyclic nitrones (3) and (4) to methoxycarbonylmethylene-cyclopropane (21) gives adducts having the methoxycarbonyl group on C-4 of the isoxazolidine ring with high regioselectivity. The thermal rearrangement of the adducts gives quinolizidinone and indolizidinones intermediates for new formal syntheses²⁸ of the alkaloids (\pm)-lupinine and (\pm)-epilupinine, (\pm)-elaekanine A, respectively. The cycloaddition between (21) and 3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-*N*-oxide (4) at 80°C in toluene gave a mixture of two diastereomeric isoxazolidines (22a) and (22b) (78%) in 2.3 : 1 ratio (Scheme 3). (3) with (21) gave a similar mixture of cycloadducts (23a) and (23b) in a 2.1 : 1 ratio (64% overall yield). H₃-H₄ (isoxazolidine

Scheme 3

numberings) coupling constant in the major compound (**23a**) 8.4 Hz vs 4.3 Hz in (**23b**) attested for the preference of an *endo* approach in the cycloaddition of this nitron.

The observed regioselectivity is in agreement with the conclusions drawn by an inspection of the coefficients and energies of the frontier molecular orbitals of (**21**) and nitron (**3**) (Fig. 5). In the favored HOMO_{nitron}-LUMO_{dipolarophile} interaction, the larger coefficients are located on the oxygen of the nitron and on the cyclopropylidene carbon of the methylenecyclopropane as required for the observed regioselectivity. A quantitative evaluation of the differences in charge transfer energies of the two regioisomeric oriented complexes ($\Delta\Delta E = \Delta E_{5\text{-spiro}} - \Delta E_{4\text{-spiro}} = -0.30 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) again predicts the 5-*spiro* regioisomer as being the dominant isomer in the cycloaddition.

Fig. 5

By heating **22(a,b)** under Flash Vacuum Thermolysis (FVT) conditions (450°C, 10^{-3} mm Hg) the quinolizidinone (**24**) and the enaminones (**26**) were obtained. Both diastereomeric isoxazolidines gave a single diastereomeric ketone probably as a result of a tautomerism towards the more stable isomer. The coupling constant of 10.9 Hz implied that the carbomethoxy group to be placed in equatorial position *cis* to the bridgehead proton. An analogous FVT treatment of isoxazolidines **23(a,b)** followed by chromatographic separation, gave both the diastereomeric indolizidinones **25(a,b)** in 2.4 : 1 ratio (45%) besides the enaminones (**27**) (19%). Again a coupling constant of 11.1 Hz testifies for *trans* H₈-H_{8a} relationship in the major isomer (**25a**)²⁸.

A new type cascade reaction of alkyne-containing *N*-hydroxypyrrolidines has been discovered²⁹, involving hydroxylaminealkyne cyclization, Cope elimination and 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition, leading eventually to the required intermediate cyclic nitron for intramolecular 1,3-dipolar

Scheme 4

trapping by the pendant butenyl dipolarophiles (Scheme 4). The cyclization mode for the preparation of (**28**) is "6-*exo-dig*" (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6

The regioselectivity for the alkene addition to the five-membered cyclic nitron is reversed from that observed for six-(**28**) or seven-membered cyclic nitron (**29**). The opposite regiochemistry of addition for the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of the proposed precursor five-membered nitron, can be rationalized by proposing a kinetically preferred cycloaddition (C-C bond leads C-O bond formation and occurs to produce the kinetically preferred ring size) for the five-membered cyclic nitron. The larger ring size however constrains the cycloaddition to occur so that the nitron oxygen attacks the non-terminal end of the double bond (Fig. 7). The "5-*exo-trig*" mode of hydroxylamine cyclization is kinetically preferred over the "5- and "7-*exo-*

dig" mode, but not the "6-*exo-dig*" mode. However, dimethyl substitution of the terminal alkene can suppress the "5-*exo-dig*" mode and therefore permit the alternative "*exo-dig*" cyclizations²⁹.

Fig. 7

Alibés *et al.*³⁰ have shown that the cycloadditions of cyclic nitrones to γ -oxo α,β -unsaturated esters presented an unexpectedly high regioselectivity, that must be attributed to steric factors. Under kinetic control, the *endo/exo* stereoselectivity is low, but it can be spectacularly improved under thermodynamic conditions. The comparatively easy reversibility of the cycloaddition, is also due to the presence of two carbonyl groups conjugated to the double bond. The reduction of the major regioisomers is a high-yielding procedure for the preparation of some hydroxylic derivatives that are not formed directly, but are obtained only as minor stereoisomers in the cycloadditions of the same nitrones to the corresponding γ -hydroxy α,β -unsaturated esters.

The regioselectivity of the 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions between simple unsubstituted nitrone, $\text{CH}_2=\text{NH}-\text{O}^-$, and electron-rich alkenes (e.g. aminoethylene) has been studied by Magnuson and Pranata³¹, using *ab initio* methods (B3LYP/6-31G*). The '*ortho*' regioisomers are predicted to be formed in a higher proportion than the '*meta*' regioisomers, calculations predict that the reactions with electron-poor alkenes such as acrylonitrile will be nonregioselective; the unsubstituted nitrone exhibits a preferred *endo* selectivity because of stabilizing secondary orbital interactions.

Domingo studied the 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions of *N*-benzylidene aniline *N*-oxide to the electron-rich olefin *tert*-butyl vinyl ether³², B3LYP/6-31G* calculations predict an *exo* stereoselectivity together with an '*ortho*' regioselectivity in agreement with experimental findings³³. The *exo* selectivity is favored, as a non-bonded steric interaction between a phenyl group on the N atom and the *tert*-butyl group of the vinyl ether progressively develops in the *endo*-approach. Inclusion of solvent effects increases the activation ener-

gies and decreases the exothermic character of the process because of a greater solvation of the polar nitrone than that of the transition states and cycloadducts^{32,34}.

The α -nitrostyrene generated *in situ* from α -halogeno oximes, underwent regioselective cycloaddition/nucleophilic reactions with *N*-arylamino 1,3-diazabuta-1,3-dienes leading to a mixture of imidazoles and cyclic nitrones³⁵. The cyclic nitrones underwent 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition with dimethylacetylenedicarboxylate (DMAD) to form the corresponding cycloadducts in moderate to high yields.

Brandi *et al.*³⁶ have demonstrated that cycloadditions of nitrone (30) to the sugar derived lactones (α,β -unsaturated C_6 -lactones) (Fig. 8) : non-chiral (32), racemic mixture (31a)/(31b), and separately D-glycero (31a) and L-glycero (31b) lactones. In the cases of (32) and (31a) high stereoselectivity was obtained and a significant kinetic resolution was observed in the case of the racemate (31a)/(31b).

Fig. 8

The *exo* approach to the *re-re* sides of the lactones predominated. It has been noted that (30) gave moderate to very good kinetic resolutions with other dipolarophiles^{37a,b}.

1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions between the D-erythrose and D-threose derived nitrones and methyl acrylate proceeded regioselectively to afford the corresponding 3,5-disubstituted diastereomeric isoxazolidines in good yields³⁸. The stereochemistry was dependent on the steric hindrance of the nitrone. The major products were found to have the C-3/C-4 *erythro* and C-3/C-5 *cis* relative configuration. Its formation can be rationalized by the less hindered *endo* attack of the *Z*-nitrone in an antiperiplanar manner with respect to the largest group of the cyclic acetal.

Domingo *et al.*³⁹ have investigated several 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions of a chiral nitrone prepared from L-erythrose. While cycloadditions to carbon-carbon multiple bonds of dipolarophiles such as ethyl acrylate, ethyl propiolate or dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate (DMAD) were poorly stereoselective, reaction with acrylonitrile was reported to provide predominantly one diastereomeric adduct. Interestingly, the regioselectivity exhibited by the two dipolarophiles ethyl acrylate and ethyl propiolate was found to be opposite. The mechanisms of these cycloadditions have thus been investigated by means of Density Functional

Theory (*DFT*) methods with the *B3LYP* function and the 6-31G* and 6-31 + G* basis sets. A simplified achiral version of the nitron derived from L-erythrose as the dipole and methyl propiolate or acrylonitrile as the dipolarophiles, were chosen as computational models. The cycloadditions have been shown to take place through one-step pathway in which the C-C and C-O σ bonds are formed simultaneously but in a nonsynchronous way. For the reaction with methyl propiolate, *DFT* calculations predict the experimentally observed 'meta' regioselectivity.

Catalytic enantioselective 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions

The catalytic enantioselective 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction has been developed to be a highly selective reaction of nitrones with electron-deficient alkenes activated by chiral Lewis acids^{40,41}. The first highly diastereo- and enantioselective catalytic 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions of cyclic nitrones activated by chiral Lewis acids with electron-rich alkene has been developed by Jørgensen and coworkers⁴². In the case of acyclic nitrones cycloadditions with alkenes catalyzed by chiral polybinaththyl Lewis acids have been developed giving isoxazolidines with up to 99% *ee*⁴³.

Cycloaddition of nitrones with an enolate group as dipolarophile was reported by Aurich *et al.*⁴⁴. (*S*)-(+)-5-Benzyl-7-hydroxy-6-methyl-5-azaheptanone-2 was prepared by nucleophilic addition of *N*-benzylalaninol to butenone. Swern oxidation gave the corresponding aldehyde which was treated with *N*-alkylhydroxylamines without isolation to afford the nitrones. These were converted to lithium enolates by reaction with lithium diisopropylamide (LDA) in tetrahydrofuran at -78°C . When the reaction mixture was allowed to warm up to RT, intramolecular cycloaddition of the enolate group to the nitron moiety occurred, affording the 4-hydroxy-4-methyl-3-oxa-2,7-diazabicyclo[3,3,0]octanes in 23 to 65% yield as diastereomerically pure optically active substances.

Highly regioselective 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions of captodative olefins 1-acetylviny carboxylates to diverse dipoles have been reported by Tamariz and coworkers⁴⁵. The reaction of (**33a**) with *C,N*-diphenyl nitron went with high regioselectivity to provide isoxazolidines **35a/36a** in 80% yield, as a mixture of stereoisomers *endo/exo* in a ratio of 89 : 11 (Scheme 5). Isomer ratios for the other *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl nitrones are in the range 85–90 : 15–10 for most reactants. The NMR spectra of crude mixtures revealed the presence of a mixture of diastereomeric isoxazolidines (**35**)/(**36**). NOE experiments established the relative configuration of the major isomer, indicating that an *endo*-transition state was favoured and according to the authors probably stabilized by secondary orbital interactions⁴⁶ (Fig. 9). It is

not certain as to how much of an electron-donor is the PNB (*p*-nitrobenzoyloxy) group, as the ester functionality is known to have very little electron-donating effect. This electron-donating effect will be further minimized by the electron-withdrawing *p*-nitrophenyl group. The lower stereoselection for olefin (**33b**) in comparison with (**33a**) would suggest that the steric hindrance between the *N*-phenyl group of the nitron and the carboxylate substituent in the dipolarophile could affect the stereochemical outcome of these reactions⁴⁶. Indeed, the more crowded *exo*-transition state for (**33a**) would lead to the preferential *endo* approach, improving (**35**)/(**36**) ratio, as observed.

Scheme 5

The high C-5 regioselectivity observed in these cycloadditions with all the dipoles could be explained by steric control, keeping the bulkier aryl group of the nitron and the *geminally* substituted carbon C-3 of the olefin as far away from each other as possible. However, steric interactions might not be the sole reason, since the more crowded C-4 substituted isomers have mainly been generated depending on the electronic demand have been reported by Houk *et al.*⁴⁷ of the dipolarophile substituents. Factors such as the captodative effect⁴⁸, involving diradicaloid intermediates or transition states, were also considered by the authors in controlling the orientation of the cycloaddends.

Fig. 9. Transition states of the cycloaddition of nitrones towards olefin (**33a**).

Merino and coworkers⁴⁹ have demonstrated the stereoselective conversion of *N*-benzyl-1,2-di-*O*-isopropylidene-D-glyceraldehyde nitron (BIGN) into *cis* and *trans*-L-isoxazolidinyl thymidine with either vinyl acetate or a vinyl base. The experimental results of the cycloaddition reactions can be qualitatively explained by theoretical *ab initio* calculations which correctly predicted the prefer-

ential formation of the major adducts since the lowest calculated transition state energy is for the *exo* approach of the dipolarophile to the *si* face of the nitron.

Pyrimido[1,4]diazepine-*N*-oxides (PDNO), the seven-membered cyclic nitrones (**39**), were prepared for the first time. Their 1,3-dipolar cycloadditive ability was shown⁵⁰ to be dependent on the degree of substitution at the C-atom of the dipole. The aldonitron (**39a**) reacted with both olefinic and acetylenic substrates whilst the ketodipole (**39b**) was inactive towards olefinic dipolarophiles. With monosubstituted (**39a**) a preference was displayed for the formation of 4-substituted isoxazolidine rings. The diastereoselectivity of the cycloaddition was lowest with methyl vinyl ketone and highest with *N*-methylmaleimide. The dimethyl fumarate cycloaddition product had a short lifetime at RT and underwent retrocycloaddition to exist in equilibrium with (**39a**) and the dipolarophile.

(39) a : R = H
b : R = Me

Solid phase synthesis

Cycloaddition reactions with one of the reactants attached to a solid support has been receiving attention in recent years. Solid phase synthesis of diverse isoxazolidines in one-pot three-component cycloaddition has been established by Jung *et al.*⁵¹ The versatility of the cycloaddition and yields of the isoxazolidines were strongly dependent on the resin-bound component. Isoxazolidines obtained by the reaction of polymer-bound hydroxylamines with aldehydes and olefins showed the highest yields and were accessible in high diversity, whereas the synthesis with polymer-bound olefins was less practicable due to the low yields. Compared to solution phase reactions, similar regio- and stereochemical results of the solid phase nitron-olefin cycloaddition were observed. The most successful reaction protocol was the reaction of polymer-bound hydroxylamines with aldehydes and alkenes using Rink amide resin. α -Bromo carboxylic acids were coupled onto Rink resin with *N,N'*-diisopropylcarbodiimide (DIC). Substitution of bromine with hydroxylamine resulted in polymer-bound *N*-substituted hydroxylamine. After condensation of an aldehyde the resulting nitron was trapped with an olefin to yield isoxazolidines. The influence of the substitution pattern and

the electronic properties of the aromatic aldehydes on the product yield was less than normally expected. Different substitution patterns had also no significant effect on this reaction. Aliphatic aldehydes showed a different behavior: the long-chain octanal gave the product in 81% yield; however, 3-phenylpropanal gave only 48% yield of the heterocycle.

Different *N*-substituted maleimides gave the best results with 78–85% yield. Strongly electron-deficient dipolarophiles like fumaric acid dinitrile or tri- and tetrasubstituted dipolarophiles like phenylene malonodinitrile or isopropylidene dimethyl-malonate reacted in low yields or not at all. Monosubstituted electron-deficient olefins like phenylvinylsulphone and acrylamide gave different results; whereas the product obtained with the sulphone showed a yield of 75%, the acrylamide gave only 46% yield due to its tendency to polymerize. Styrenes participated well in these reactions, though the reaction time had to be extended to 18 h at 80°C. The electron-rich styrenes like the 2,3-dimethoxystyrene gave the best results.

The kinetics of the solid phase cycloaddition was studied⁵¹ by the addition of *N*-methylmaleimide to the polymer-bound nitron as in the sequel (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6

A number of 1,3-DCs were achieved under thermal conditions; traces of the polymer-support remained even after cleavage. Kobayashi *et al.*^{52a,b} has developed a Lewis-acid mediated pathway for carrying out cycloadditions of polymer-supported nitrones with alkenes. A catalytic amount of $\text{Yb}(\text{OTf})_3$ was used to mediate the cycloadditions. The 3-acyl-1,3-oxazolin-2-one group could be converted to various functional groups on the solid-phase support. In these reactions, alkenes in the presence of $\text{Yb}(\text{OTf})_3$ reacted smoothly with nitrones generated *in situ* from aldehydes and hydroxylamines.

Reactions of *C*-(1-methylindol-3-yl)-*N*-methyl nitron⁵³

with the carbonyl dipolarophiles gave cycloadducts in good to high yields (55–93 %). The reaction of nitron with dimethyl fumarate was highly diastereoselective and gave the two diastereoisomers and in a relative ratio of 10 : 1. The reaction of the same nitron with dimethyl maleate was less diastereoselective and the diastereoisomers being obtained in the ratio of 1.6 : 1.

The regioselectivity of the reactions is also in accordance with that usually observed in the reactions of nitrones with acrylates and vinylketones. The formation of 5-substituted isoxazolidines favored by LUMO_{dipole} interaction, predominates. 4-Substituted isoxazolidines, which are favored by a HOMO_{dipole} interaction are usually the minor products⁵⁴.

Quite recently, an efficient and straightforward synthesis of the new captodative olefins, *N*-substituted 5-alkylidene-1,3-oxazolidine-2,4-diones, by chemoselective oxidative cleavage of novel *exo*-2-oxazolidinone dienes have been described by Tamariz and coworkers⁵⁵.

Earlier it had been observed that the intramolecular 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of the nitron (40) produced, in a highly stereoselective manner, the bicyclic isoxazolidine (41), convertible into β -methylcarbapenem (42), while the corresponding fluorinated nitron (43) gave a 1 : 2.8 mixture of two stereoisomers (44) and (45)⁵⁶. The results could be explained by considering that the desired stereoisomer (41) was diastereoselectively formed via conformation (47), this having the least 1,3-allylic strain. However, conformation (48) was not favorable for the fluorinated compound mainly because of the dipole repulsion between the fluorine atom and the oxygen atom of the nitron; therefore, the alternative conformation (46) became the preferred one (Scheme 7)⁵⁶.

Scheme 7

1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition of nitrones possessing a fluorine atom at the C-2 position have been studied by Fukumoto *et al.*⁵⁷. It is clear that the role of 1,2-asymmetric induction on the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of nitrones is influenced by the presence of a fluorine atom at the C-2 position⁵⁷. These cycloadducts would be useful as precursors of pharmacologically interesting compounds, such as fluoroamino acids.

Theoretical calculations

While a huge amount of theoretical work has been done on Diels-Alder reaction, there were very few papers which theoretically analyzed 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions. Recently, however, a number of such papers have appeared. These are summarized in some details below.

Semi-empirical quantum mechanical methods (AM1) were used by Fišera *et al.*⁵⁸ to rationalize the regio- and stereoselectivity of nitron cycloadditions. Diarylnitrones (49) react regioselectively with 3,3-methylene-5,5-dimethyl-2-pyrrolidinone (48) to give a mixture of diastereomeric spiro-cycloadducts (50) and (51), in which (50) always dominates. AM1 calculations for these reactions showed that the regio- and stereochemistry of the nitron cycloadditions seems to be controlled by steric effects. Comparison with the unsubstituted derivative (48a) showed a decrease of diastereoselectivity in the cycloaddition for the derivatives, 48(b-g) possessing a substituent at the nitrogen (Scheme 8).

Scheme 8

The cycloaddition of (48a,b) and (48f) with *C,C*-diphenyl-*N*-methylnitron (52) proceeded analogously to give cycloadducts (53). On the other hand, cycloadditions of *C*-(aroyl)-*N*-phenyl-nitrones (55) and 48(a-g) afforded exclusively the *spiro*-isoxazolidines (56) (Scheme 9).

In order to rationalize the high regio- and stereoselectivity of benzoylnitron cycloadditions, quantum mechanical calculations of a model reaction between (48a)

and (55y) were performed using the semi-empirical AM1 method. The frontier orbital energies of dipolarophile (48a) and dipole (55) are as follows :

$$E_{\text{HOMO}}(48a) = -9.94 \text{ eV} \quad E_{\text{HOMO}}(55a) = -9.40 \text{ eV}$$

$$E_{\text{LUMO}}(48a) = 0.37 \text{ eV} \quad E_{\text{LUMO}}(55b) = -0.94 \text{ eV}$$

The energy difference between LUMO-dipole and HOMO-dipolarophile (9.00 eV) is somewhat lower than between HOMO-dipole and LUMO-dipolarophile (9.77 eV). According to this data, it may seem that the reaction should mainly be controlled by the LUMO of dipole (55b),

but this orbital is delocalized throughout the whole π system with only minor contributions of the nitron moiety. The HOMO of dipolarophile (48a) is localized on the ring nitrogen and has lone-pair character. On the basis of this, these authors concluded that the reaction is controlled actually by the HOMO of dipole (55a). Indeed, the LUMO of (48a) and the HOMO of (55a) are localized mostly on the reacting atoms. The HOMO MO coefficient of the nitron carbon is 0.69, that of the oxygen -0.56 . In the LUMO of dipolarophile (48a) the coefficient of the terminal methylene carbon is calculated to be larger than that of the ring carbon (0.66 and -0.52 , respectively). When these orbitals are taken into account, a simple FMO analysis reveals that regioisomers with the oxygen of nitron group bound to the *spiro* carbon, should be preferred.

1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions of nitrones to alkenyl derivative (48b) proceed in a chemoselective manner to yield only the cycloadducts to the exocyclic double bond. The cycloadducts which could be formed by the attack of nitrones to the double bond of the alkenyl chain in (48b) have not been detected in the crude reaction mixture. This can be explained by the well-known fact that angular strain in a dipolarophile increases its reactivity⁵⁸.

Cycloaddition of *C,N*-diaryl nitrones to 4-methy-

lenetetrahydrothiopyran (58) proceeds regioselectively in toluene at 110°C to yield *spiro* isoxazolidine derivatives (Scheme 10). Semi-empirical calculations (AM1) were used to explain the electronic structure of reactants, energy of products and activation barriers leading to these products. It was prepared by these authors⁵⁹ that the main factor responsible for high selectivity is not frontier orbital control, but mainly electrostatic and steric interactions.

Matsuoka and coworkers⁶⁰ reported that the cycloaddition proceeds with nearly synchronous mechanism and the calculation can well reproduce the charge transfer (CT) complexation observed prior to the primary cycloaddition. To elucidate mechanistic aspects of the primary cycloaddition, *ab initio* and PM3 methods were used⁶¹. The fully optimized calculation resulting by the MP2/6-31G*, HF/6-31G and 3-21G* level for transition structure (TS115), (60), (61) and the cycloadduct (62) were done. From the MP2/6-31G* calculations of (TS115), the length of the newly forming bonds of O-C and C-N were obtained as 1.740 and 2.197 Å respectively, this indicated that the former bond formation is significantly advanced than that of the latter. The activation enthalpy from the reactants [(60) + (61)] was 17.63 kcal mol⁻¹ (MP2/6-31G*).

Fig. 9a. Structure TS115 by MP2/6-31G*.

A study of the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition behavior of a series of substituted 3,4-dihydroisoquinoline-*N*-oxides with electron-deficient allenes has been carried out by Eguchi *et al.*⁶² The 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction proceeded in high yield with complete regioselectivity to give 5-methylene isoxazolidines. The stability of these 5-methylene isoxazolidines depended on the structure of nitrones and allenes. The rearrangements of 5-*exo* methylene isoxazolidines are not only particularly sensitive to the kind of the substituent groups on the double bond, but also obviously affected by the structure of the nitrone. Based on FMO theory, allenes possessing electron-withdrawing substituents are expected to react more readily and to undergo 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction across the activated C₁-C₂ π-bond. MNDO calculations of several substituted allenes indicate that the introduction of an electron-withdrawing group on the double bond causes a significant lowering of the LUMO energy level compared with parent allene and the largest LUMO coefficient resides on the central carbon and the next on the position bearing the activating group. Hence, the reaction of *C*-phenyl-*N*-methyl nitrone with electron-deficient allenes proceeded in a highly regioselective fashion and gave rise to the 5-*exo* methylene isoxazolidine. This was also the case when substituted 3,4-dihydroisoquinoline-*N*-oxides were used. The nitrone-HOMO dipolarophile-LUMO interaction has the smallest energy difference. Nitrone cycloaddition reactions may proceed through *exo*- or *endo*-transition states as for Diels-Alder reactions. A generally accepted view of these reactions involves an approach of the addends in two parallel planes. A possibility of nitrone *E*-*Z* isomerization can give rise to four kinds of transition state i.e. *E-endo*, *E-exo*, *Z-endo* and *Z-exo*. Here, because configurationally fixed nitrones were employed, only two kinds of transition state can be expected to occur, i.e., *E-endo* and *E-exo*. Thus the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction of substituted 3,4-dihydroisoquinoline-*N*-oxides with electron-deficient allenes proceeded in high yield with complete regioselectivity to give 5-*exo* methylene isoxazolidines which were the stable isolated products, rearranged Δ⁴-isoxazoline (by 1,3-hydrogen shift) or rearranged pyrrolidinones (by N-O bond scission) depending on both the structures of nitrones and allenes.

The 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of thiazolyl nitrones with chiral acrylates has been studied⁶³. The reaction of *N*-benzyl nitrone and its *p*-methoxy derivative in the synthesis of α-amino-2-alkylthiazoles through 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition with activated alkenes followed by the cleavage of the resulting isoxazolidines.

It has been found that the cycloadditions occur with good regio- and diastereoselectivity favoring the formation of the *trans* 3,5-disubstituted isoxazolidines. The regioselectivity can be rationalized by considering the calculated coefficients in the frontier molecular orbitals (AM1, MOPAC6) for the nitrone and the acrylate corresponding to the most favored interaction, in this case HOMO_{dipole} – LUMO_{dipolarophile} (Fig. 10). An alternative explanation has been proposed in which the reactivity is controlled by the HOMO_{dipole} – LUMO_{dipolarophile} interaction, whilst the regioselectivity is determined by the reverse interaction, viz. LUMO_{dipole} – HOMO_{dipolarophile}. Furthermore, the diastereoselectivity was explained by *endo* approach of the olefin to the *Z*-nitrone (*Z-endo* approach) (Fig. 11) due to secondary orbital interactions between the *p*-orbitals of the nitrone nitrogen and the carbonyl group of the dipolarophile.

Fig. 10. Calculated FMO energies and atomic coefficients.

Fig. 11. *Z-endo* approach of nitrone to acrylates.

For asymmetric thermal reactions of *N*-acryloyl derivatives of the Oppolzer's camphor sultam, the observed stereoselectivity is in the line with the model of Kim and Curran⁶⁴. Accordingly the *Z-endo* attack should take place on the "top face" of the most favored *anti*-, *s-cis* rotamer (Fig. 12), thus leading to (3*R*, 5*R*)-isoxazolidines as the major products.

Fig. 12

The 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of C_2 -symmetric dipolarophile with nitrones is a rare example of a, 1,1-disubstituted olefin reacting regioselectively to give 4,4- rather than 5,5-disubstituted isoxazolidines. Aggarwal *et al.*⁶⁵ have reported that the C_2 -symmetric dipolarophile adds to both acyclic and cyclic nitrones with very high stereoselectivity. The reactions were conducted in dichloromethane at room temperature using 5 molar equivalents of nitron. Product ratios were determined by ^1H NMR integration of crude reaction mixture.

The observed stereoselectivity was rationalized by considering the possible transition states of the reaction. Due to the C_2 -symmetry element present in the dipolarophile, only two transition states are possible, leading to the diastereomeric 4-substituted isoxazolidines (**63**) and (**64**) (Fig. 13). Transition state (TS1) leads to the observed product (**63**). The alternative transition state (TS2) suffers from steric and electronic repulsions between the phenyl ring of the nitron and the sulphanyl oxygen; in transition state (TS1) the phenyl group approaches over a sulphanyl lone pair and the oxygen of the second sulphoxide over the smaller hydrogen atom. Selectivities in cycloadditions are often much higher than with acyclic nitrones due to the absence of *E-Z* isomerization in the dipole. Furthermore, with non-conjugated monosubstituted olefins, reactions have been shown to proceed preferentially via *exo*-transition states affording *trans*-adducts; *endo*-transition states are disfavoured by steric interactions of substituents on the dipolarophile with methylene groups on the ring. It was of interest therefore to investigate how a 1,1-disubstituted dipolarophile in which one substituent must always interact to some extent with the dipole ring, would react with such nitrones⁶⁵.

Basing arguments on considerations of crystal structure, a stereochemical rationale could again be proposed for 1,3-

Fig. 13

dipolar cycloadditions of cyclic nitrones. The two possible transition states leading to the two diastereomeric isoxazolidines (**65**) and (**66**) are shown in Fig. 14. To account for the observed selectivity, transition state TS3 must be favored over TS4. Presumably the unfavorable steric interactions in TS3 are even more pronounced in TS4, where the "offending" oxygen approaches over the bulk, rather than the periphery, of the nitron ring. The higher selectivity observed in the case of (**5**) (Fig. 4) may be due to an additional electronic repulsion in transition state TS4 between the sulphanyl-oxygen lone pair and the π -system of the aromatic ring⁶⁶.

Fig. 14

Scheeren and coworkers⁶⁷ have reported the first examples of chiral Lewis acid catalyzed 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of nitrones with ketene acetals. The reactivity of nitrones toward ketene acetals was considerably enhanced by applying chiral oxazaborolidines as Lewis acid catalysts at -78°C . The chiral Lewis acid is assumed to complex with the nitron oxygen atom, by which the LUMO energy of the nitron is lowered to give a $\text{LUMO}_{\text{nitron}}$ controlled enantioselective reaction with the electron-rich ketene acetals. Some examples of chiral Lewis acid catalyzed $\text{HOMO}_{\text{nitron}}$ controlled 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions with electron-deficient dipolarophiles were reported⁶⁸. 1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions of various nitrones with vinyl ethers are catalyzed by Lewis acids e.g. chiral oxazaborolidines, proceed with complete regioselectivity, but with poor stereoselectivity to give mixtures of *cis*- and *trans*-5-ethoxyisoxazolidines. In all cases the enantioselectivity is very low. The non-catalyzed high pressure promoted reaction gives predominantly the *cis* isomer. The yields have to be optimized using longer times and/or higher pressures. The chiral oxazaborolidine catalyzed *exo*-selective cycloaddition of pyrroline-*N*-oxide with excess 2,3-dihydrofuran affords a